

To Evaluate the Serum Levels of suPAR and Interlukin-6 and Their Associations to Severity in Chronic Obstructive Pulmonary Disease Patients: A Case Control Study

S.N. Manidevi Karampudi¹, Shivprasad S², Sagar H³, Harish G Bagewadi⁴,
Devendrappa B G⁵, Shivalee. A⁶, Rohini Kallur⁷

¹Associate Professor, Department of Pulmonary medicine, Gulbarga Institute of Medical Sciences, Kalaburagi

²Associate Professor, Department of Biochemistry, Gulbarga Institute of Medical Sciences, Kalaburagi

³Assistant Professor, Department of General Medicine, Gulbarga Institute of Medical Sciences, Kalaburagi

⁴Associate Professor, Department of Pharmacology, Gulbarga Institute of Medical Sciences, Kalaburagi

⁵Biostatistician, Department of Community Medicine, Gulbarga Institute of Medical Sciences, Kalaburagi, India

⁶Research Scientist, Multi -Disciplinary Research Unit, GIMS, Kalaburagi, India

⁷Research Scientist, Multi -Disciplinary Research Unit, GIMS, Kalaburagi, India

Received: 20-07-2024 / Revised: 30-07-2024 / Accepted: 29-08-2024

Corresponding Author: Dr. Harish G Bagewadi

Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:

Background: Chronic Obstructive Pulmonary Disease (COPD) is characterized by an abnormal inflammatory response of airways. The disease progress can be diagnosed at the early stage of pulmonary inflammation by using a novel biomarkers like soluble urokinase-type plasminogen activator receptor (suPAR) and Interleukin-6.

Materials and Methods: Study participants were grouped into cases- COPD (n=35) and healthy controls (n=35) and recruited for the study after obtaining informed consent. As specified by GOLD criteria, COPD group participants were graded into grades I-IV. Serum suPAR and IL-6 assays were done for all the study participants.

Results: The level of suPAR among COPD grades I-IV (5.75±0.544 ng/ml; 5.88±0.942 ng/ml; 6.78±1.05 ng/ml; 15.0±15.8 ng/ml respectively) were high compared to healthy controls (4.12± 6.17 ng/ml) and was statistically significant. The levels of IL-6 among COPD grade I-IV (8.06± 0.839 pg/ml; 11.0±2.40 pg/ml; 12.9±3.76 pg/ml; 13.4±2.67 pg/ml respectively) were high compared to healthy controls (4.37± 1.44 pg/ml) and was statistically significant. The spirometry readings- FEV1, FVC values were significantly lower among patients with COPD when compared with the healthy controls (P<0.05). It was observed that an inverse correlation was found between serum level of suPAR, IL-6 levels versus FEV1, FVC values which was statistically significant (p<0.05). Our study indicated that serum suPAR and IL-6 may play an important role in the inflammatory process of COPD particularly in grades II, III and IV COPD. Hence, serum suPAR and IL-6 measurements may be useful for the evaluation and prognosis of COPD patients.

Conclusion: We conclude that cases of moderate to severe grades of COPD with greater degrees of obstruction of the airways have higher levels of suPAR, IL-6 in serum. The serum levels of these cytokines can therefore be utilized as the clinical and prognostic parameters for evaluation of the disease severity and tailored therapy for the same.

Keywords: COPD, suPAR, IL-6, Novel Biomarkers.

This is an Open Access article that uses a funding model which does not charge readers or their institutions for access and distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>) and the Budapest Open Access Initiative (<http://www.budapestopenaccessinitiative.org/read>), which permit unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided original work is properly credited.

Introduction

Chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD) is a common and treatable non-communicable disease characterized by progressive airflow limitation and tissue destruction. It is associated with structural lung changes due to chronic inflammation from prolonged exposure to noxious particles. Chronic inflammation causes airway narrowing and de-

creased lung recoil. The disease often presents with symptoms of cough, dyspnea and sputum production. Symptoms can range from being asymptomatic to respiratory failure. [1] The diagnosis of COPD is based on respiratory symptoms, persistent airflow obstruction and the presence of causative agents such as the inhalation of multiple pollutants,

primarily tobacco. [2] Conventionally, the tool used to diagnose stable COPD is the forced expiratory volume in the first second of expiration (FEV1). Owing to lack of available diagnostic laboratory tests, acute exacerbation- COPD are often diagnosed based on clinical symptoms, which is subjective and is prone to inter-observer variations. Therefore, there is a need for a better tool for the diagnosis of COPD and to monitor its prognosis and severity. However, the biomarkers used to assist the diagnosis and prediction of COPD is still insufficient. [3] Determination of the serum level of suPAR could play an important role in the evaluation of patients with stable COPD. [4]

Soluble urokinase-type plasminogen activator receptor (suPAR) is a soluble form of the urokinase plasminogen activator receptor (suPAR), which is released by membrane-bound plasminogen activator and is positively correlated with the activation of the immune system. [5]

In recent years, it has become a potential inflammation biomarker. [6] Airway inflammation plays an important role in the development of COPD. The prognostic value of suPAR level among COPD patients may aid in the early diagnosis of underlying pulmonary low grade inflammation, thus allowing the physicians to provide targeted therapies and avoiding unnecessary side-effects of prolonged exposure to drugs, and also avoiding incomplete treatment of COPD. [7] suPAR estimation has been found to have a diagnostic and prognostic role in sepsis and acute exacerbation of COPD. [8]

The disease progress can be diagnosed at the early stage of pulmonary inflammation by using a novel biomarker, like Soluble urokinase-type plasminogen activator receptor (suPAR) released from the respiratory epithelium in COPD and this suPAR is a novel biomarker expected to facilitate the diagnosis of COPD and to predict the prognosis after treatment. [9] suPAR is a novel biomarker of low-grade pulmonary inflammation which is usually associated with the pathogenesis of lung disease. As a potential biologically stable marker, suPAR is being used clinically to predict the prognosis for sepsis, congestive heart failure and ARDS. [10]

IL-6 is mainly produced by T cells and macrophages. It is one of the interleukins that works as a pro-inflammatory cytokine. [11] IL-6 was found to be elevated in exacerbation of COPD and is found in the exhaled breath condensate and sputum during exacerbation and stability. [12] The presence of IL-6 in the airways of COPD is usually associated with sustained inflammation. [13] Some studies emphasized the association between IL-6 and poor clinical outcomes in patients with COPD. [14] Different studies highlighted the important

role of IL-6 as an inflammatory marker in COPD, as presented by the meta-analysis and systematic review done by Wei et al. [15] Some studies in the literature have indicated that IL-6 levels were significantly elevated in the peripheral blood of patients with COPD and it was associated with FEV1. [16] In a study done by De Moraes et al. [17] it was found that a greater number of exacerbations per year may be related to systemic inflammation and it may indicate increased inflammatory activity in these patients, which can persist after recovery. In another study done by Bolton et al. [18] it was determined that IL-6 is increased in patients with COPD and has a role in the control of the acute inflammatory response. The airflow limitation in COPD patients is due to the increase in the resistance to airflow, which is caused by smooth muscle hypertrophy, goblet cell metaplasia, degeneration of the airway cartilage, and mucous hypersecretion. [19] In a previous study done by Chen et al, [20] it was observed that IL-6 was the best systemic inflammatory cytokine to reflect the dyspnea and pulmonary function. It is hence reasonable to speculate that circulating IL-6 is a promising novel clinical biomarker in predicting the risk and severity of COPD. There are no previous studies in the literature to assess the prognosis and severity in chronic obstructive pulmonary disease patients by serum estimation of suPAR and IL-6 levels.

To fill up this gap in the literature and to explore the newer inflammatory biomarkers in COPD patients, we have conducted this present study which might aid to the better understanding in pathophysiology, prognosis and severity of COPD disease patients which will help in delivering better treatment outcomes in near future. Hence, this study was conducted to compare serum suPAR and IL-6 levels in COPD patients in order to assess the prognosis and severity.

Aims and Objectives

1. To estimate the serum levels of suPAR
2. To estimate the serum levels of Interleukin-6 (IL-6)
3. To evaluate the associations of serum levels suPAR and (IL-6) to clinical severity in chronic Obstructive pulmonary disease patients.

Materials and Methods

This was a hospital based case control study. The study participants were recruited from OPD and IPD of department of pulmonary medicine. The study was done from May 2023 to July 2024. Institutional Ethics Committee approval was taken before the conduct of the study.

Written informed consent was obtained from all the subjects before their participation. In this study, a total of 70 subjects were recruited. Study

participants were grouped into stable chronic obstructive pulmonary disease patients (n=35) and apparently healthy controls (n=35).

Inclusion Criteria: Stable chronic obstructive pulmonary disease patients with history of dyspnoea, chronic cough and sputum production for a period of 3 months for 2 consecutive years and apparently healthy controls aged between 30-65 years inclusive of both sexes were included and matched in the study.

Exclusion Criteria: Subjects with history of bronchial asthma, bronchiectasis, tuberculosis, cystic fibrosis, sepsis, acute respiratory distress syndrome, cirrhosis of liver and chronic renal failure, ischemic heart disease, heart failure, cancer patients, autoimmune or connective tissue disorders, patients receiving steroids, immunosuppressant drugs and pregnant women were excluded from the study.

Sample size calculation was performed. The study measurable parameters had 5% margin of error, with 5% prevalence rate of COPD in a previous study done by Ashwani Verma, et al. [21] With the % of controls exposed is 40%, odds ratio of 5, ratio of controls to cases is 1 and with a power of 80% and 95% confidence interval (Z score of 1.96). By substituting the values, we calculated a sample size of 35 cases and 35 controls. Total sample size = 70. General information such as age, gender, occupation, literacy status, smoking status and socio-economic status was collected. After taking informed consent, a detailed clinical history was recorded of each patient and relevant clinical examination was done. Chest radiographs was taken to correlate clinically. Chest radiological examination, Posterior-anterior (PA) view was performed in every patient to assess the COPD prognosis and correlating it clinically. The parameters which was noted are: Chest x-rays may show hyperinflation, flatten-

ing of the diaphragm, and increased anterior-posterior diameter, tubular heart. [22] The study participants were subjected to clinical, chest radiological examination and were then grouped into grades I - IV as per Global Initiative for Obstructive Lung Disease (GOLD) criteria. [23] COPD grading and severity was done according to the following: I-mild COPD- which shows FEV1 more than or equal to 80% predicted, II- moderate COPD - with measurement of 50% more than or equal to FEV1 less than 80% predicted, III- severe COPD- with measurement of 30% more than or equal to FEV1 less than 50% predicted, and IV-very severe COPD, with FEV1 less than 30% predicted. [24] Pulmonary function tests to determine pulmonary function parameters like Forced expiratory volume in the 1st second (FEV1), Forced Vital Capacity (FVC), FEV1/FVC ratio, peak expiratory flow rate (PEFR) were calculated with the help of spirometer. Biochemical measurements: The blood sample (5ml) was withdrawn from all subjects by vein puncture. The blood was placed in plain tubes. The blood sample was centrifuged (at 3000 rpm for 10 minutes). The serum samples was stored at (-20°C) for the estimation of serum suPAR and IL-6 levels. Serum suPAR, IL-6 concentrations was determined using a commercially available ELISA, kit measurements was according to the kit instructions.

Statistical Analysis: The quantitative variables were expressed as mean \pm SD. The qualitative variables were expressed as counts and percentages. The difference between control group and different grades stable chronic obstructive pulmonary disease patients was analyzed using unpaired student's t-test. p value \leq 0.05 was considered as statistically significant. Statistical analysis was performed using the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) software version 27.

Results

Table 1: Demographic characteristics of the study population.

Items-	Descriptive characteristics	Control (n=35) Mean \pm SD	COPD (n=35) Mean \pm SD
Age	(years)	48.77 \pm 1.22	63.17 \pm 0.56
Gender	Male	10 (28.6%)	19 (54.3%)
	Female	25 (71.4%)	16 (45.7%)
Heart rate	Basal (bpm)	80.22 \pm .52	88.34 \pm 0.74
Smoking status	Smoker	02 (5.7%)	27 (77.2%)
	Non-smoker	33 (94.3%)	8 (22.8%)

Table 1. Shows the demographic characteristics of all the healthy controls and patients with COPD. Their mean age among the healthy controls was 48.77 \pm 1.22 years and it was 63.17 \pm 0.56 years among COPD patients. Among the COPD patients, males were 54.3% whereas 45.7% were females. In COPD patients, 77.2% were smokers and 22.8% were non-smokers.

Table 2: Pulmonary function test parameters of the study participants

PFT parameters	Controls (n=35) Mean ± SD	COPD (n=35) Mean ± SD	P - value
FEV1	85.8± 5.26	43.5± 6.02 ^{††}	p<0.001
FVC	109± 8.80	75.3± 8.23 ^{††}	p<0.001
FEV1/FVC	82.8± 8.66	50.9± 8.22 [†]	p<0.01
PEFR	88.1± 8.20	39.2± 6.92 ^{††}	p<0.001

[†]p<0.01, ^{††}p<0.001 versus control group

Table 2. Shows all the data of spirometry readings, including FEV1, FVC, FEV1/FVC and PEFR values. The values were lower significantly among patients with COPD when compared with the healthy ones (P<0.05).

Table 3: Comparison of Serum suPAR level and IL-6 among different grades of COPD and control participants.

Serum Biomarker	Controls (n=35) Mean ± SD	GOLD stage classification of COPD (Mean±SD)			
		I (n=4)	II (n=10)	III (n=15)	IV (n=6)
suPAR (ng/ml)	4.12± 6.17	5.75 ±0.544	5.88±0.942*	6.78±1.05 [†]	15.0±15.8 ^{††}
IL-6 (pg/ml)	4.37± 1.44	8.06± 0.839	11.0±2.40*	12.9±3.76 [†]	13.4±2.67 ^{††}

*p<0.01, [†]p<0.01, ^{††}p<0.001 versus control group

Table 3. Represents the Mean ± SD values for serum suPAR and IL-6 levels among different COPD grades and controls. Patients with COPD were subdivided according to disease severity into mild (4 patients, 11.4%), moderate (10 patients, 28.6%), severe (15 patients, 42.9%), and very

severe (06 patients, 17.1%). It was observed that levels of suPAR and IL-6 among COPD were high compared to healthy control. In addition, Serum suPAR and IL-6 levels were high among GOLD IV and III compared to GOLD II and I, which was statistically significant (p<0.05).

Table 4: Correlation between serum level of suPAR and Interleukin 6 and the spirometric parameters in the chronic obstructive pulmonary disease group.

PFT parameters	Correlation- Coefficient, r -value)		p-value
	- suPAR	- IL-6	
FEV1	-0.84	-0.87	<0.03
			<0.03
FVC	-0.155	-0.38	<0.02
			<0.001
FEV1/FVC	-0.02	-0.116	0.88
			0.24
PEFR	-0.279	-0.749	<0.05
			0.116

In Table 4, it was observed that an inverse correlation was found between serum level of suPAR, IL-6 levels versus FEV1, FVC, which was statistically significant (p<0.05). There was an inverse correlation was found between serum level of suPAR, IL-6 levels versus FEV1/ FVC, but it was not statistically significant. There was an inverse correlation was found between serum level of suPAR versus PEFR value which was statistically significant (p<0.05). However an inverse correlation was found between serum levels of IL-6 levels versus PEFR but the values were not significant statistically.

Discussion

In the present study, a significant decrease was found in the pulmonary functions of severe COPD patients when compared with mild and moderate COPD patients and controls. The findings of the present study are consistent with those of previous

studies which found that pulmonary function data (FEV1, FVC, FEV1%) were significantly lower in COPD patients when compared with controls. [25] The extent of inflammation, fibrosis, and luminal exudates in the small airways is correlated with the reduction in FEV1 and FEV1%. The airflow limitation in COPD patients is due to the increase in the resistance to airflow, which is caused by smooth muscle hypertrophy, goblet cell metaplasia, degeneration of the airway cartilage, and mucous hypersecretion. [26]

In our study it was observed that, the plasma suPAR level was higher among COPD grade III and IV compared to grade I, II and healthy controls. This indicates the role of urokinase plasminogen activator system in lung parenchymal destruction and small airway fibrosis. Similar finding has been reported by Can U et al., who

observed that serum suPAR was high among grade III and IV than grade I,II and control groups. [27]

Moreover, the raised suPAR level in COPD participants in our study could be due to increased expression of suPAR in the small airway epithelia and pulmonary epithelial-mesenchymal transition process among COPD patients. This can lead to disease progression and it could also be due to increased expression of urokinase plasminogen activator receptor in the small airway epithelia of COPD patients which contributes for the airflow limitation due to activation of inflammatory immune response. Similar finding is reported by a study done by Godtfredsen et al., which shows suPAR level was higher among grade IV COPD when compared to grade I-III and normal subjects. [28] Similarly, meta-analysis has shown that serum suPAR was high among grade IV compared to grade I and the level of suPAR correlated with diseases severity hence suPAR was suggested to be used clinically to monitor COPD patients on treatment and their prognosis. [29]

In our study, there was a statistically significantly higher mean of IL-6 level among COPD cases with a p-value < 0.05. The results were consistent with the findings of some previous studies done by De Moraes MR et al. [30] It demonstrated that IL-6 blood levels were significantly elevated in patients with COPD compared to those in healthy subjects, which suggests that systemic inflammatory activity exists in stable COPD patients. A meta-analysis of 33 studies, performed by Wei et al found evidence for elevated levels of serum IL-6 in COPD patients compared to healthy controls. However, no association was found between lung function decline and IL-6 levels. [31] In a more recent study by Singh et al. in 384 COPD patients were compared with 50 healthy controls. Serum levels of IL-6 were significantly ($p < 0.05$) higher among mild, moderate, severe and very severe COPD patients. Furthermore results showed a negative correlation between serum IL-6 and FEV1, FEV1 predicted and FEV1/FVC values. [32]

Regarding the relationship between serum IL-6 and spirometry findings, our study demonstrated that there was a significant negative correlation between IL-6 serum level and FEV1, FVC, values. This finding is in agreement with previous study done by Soler et al., [33] which found a negative significant correlation between IL-6 levels and FEV1%.

These our study findings are in accordance with previous studies done by Pinto-Plata et al. [34], Abd El-Maksoud et al. [35], Attaran et al. [36] and Ramadan et al. [37] which infer the significant negative correlation between IL-6 levels and FEV1. In contrast to our results, Akbulut et al. [38] found no correlation between the IL-6 value and FEV1

and FEV1/FVC values. From the previous correlations, it is clear that the increase in serum inflammatory markers has a direct correlation with the severity of COPD. The increase in these proinflammatory cytokines is correlated to the severity of COPD and is believed to contribute to the systemic comorbidities associated with COPD.

Conclusion

The study results support that suPAR and IL-6 can be used as surrogate biomarker to predict the inflammatory changes among COPD patients. Further, prospective studies need to be conducted to explore whether suPAR, IL-6 can be used as independent novel biomarkers in predicting the severity of COPD in the early stages of disease

Acknowledgments: Authors acknowledge the Department of Health Research (DHR), New Delhi, India for providing the research funding and facilities at Multi-disciplinary Research Unit (MRU), Gulbarga Institute of Medical Sciences, Kalaburagi for the research project.

References

1. Singh D, Agusti A, Anzueto A, Barnes PJ, Bourbeau J, Celli BR, et al. Global Strategy for the Diagnosis, Management, and Prevention of Chronic Obstructive Lung Disease: the GOLD science committee report 2019. *Eur Respir J*. 2019; 53(5): 1-12.
2. Vogelmeier CF, Criner GJ, Martinez FJ, Anzueto A, Barnes PJ, Bourbeau J, et al. Global strategy for the diagnosis, management, and prevention of chronic obstructive lung disease 2017 report: GOLD executive summary. *Arch Bronconeumol* 2017;53:128-49
3. Jiang Y, Xiao W, Zhang Y, Xing Y. Urokinase-type plasminogen activator system and human cationic antimicrobial protein 18 in serum and induced sputum of patients with chronic obstructive pulmonary disease. *Respirology*. 2010; 15(6):939-46.
4. Can U, Guzelant A, Yerlikaya FH, Yosunkaya S. The role of serum soluble urokinase-type plasminogen activator receptor in stable chronic obstructive pulmonary disease. *J Invest Med*. 2014; 62(7):938-43.
5. Backes Y, van der Sluijs KF, Tuij de Boer AM, Hofstra JJ, Vlaar AP, Determann RM, et al. Soluble urokinase-type plasminogen activator receptor levels in patients with burn injuries and inhalation trauma requiring mechanical ventilation: an observational cohort study. *Crit Care*. 2011; 15(R270):2-11.
6. Backes Y, van der Sluijs KF, Mackie DP, Tacke F, Koch A, Tenhunen JJ et al. Usefulness of suPAR as a biological marker in patients with systemic inflammation or infection: a systematic review. *Intensive Care Med*. 2012; 38(9):1418-28.

7. Reilly JJ, Silverman EK, Shapiro SD. Chronic Obstructive Pulmonary disease. In: Kasper DL, Fauci AS, Hauser SL, Longo DL, Jameson JL, Loscalzo J, editors. Harrison's principles of internal medicine. 19th edition. Newyork: The McGraw-Hill Companies. 2015; (2):1700-7.
8. Kurtipek E, Kesli R, Bekci TT, Eroglu F, Akin B, Kurku H, et al. Assessment of soluble urokinase-type plasminogen activator receptor (suPAR) in chronic obstructive pulmonary disease. *International Archives of Medicine*. 2015; 8:1755-7682.
9. Solberg H, Ploug M, Hansen G, Nielsen BS, Lund LR. The murine receptor for urokinase-type plasminogen activator is primarily expressed in tissues actively undergoing remodeling. *J Histochem Cytochem*. 2001; 49(2):23 7-46.
10. Donadello K, Scolletta S, Covajes C, Vincent JL. SuPAR as a prognostic biomarker in sepsis. *BMC Medicine*. 2012; 10:2-9.
11. Pinto-Plata V, Casanova C, Mullerova H, de Torres JP, Corado H, Varo N, et al. Inflammatory and repair serum biomarker pattern. Association to clinical outcomes in COPD. *Respir Res* 2012; 13(71):1-8.
12. Agusti AGN, Noguera A, Sauleda J, Sala E, Pons J, Busquets X. Systemic effects of chronic obstructive pulmonary disease. *Eur Respir J*. 2003; 21:347–360.
13. Rincon M, Irvin CG. Role of IL-6 in asthma and other inflammatory pulmonary diseases. *Int J Biol Sci*. 2012; 8:1281–1290.
14. Agusti A, Edwards LD, Rennard SI, MacNee W, Tal-Singer R, Miller BE, et al. Evaluation of COPD Longitudinally to Identify Predictive Surrogate Endpoints (ECLIPSE) Investigators. Persistent systemic inflammation is associated with poor clinical outcomes in COPD: a novel phenotype. *PLoS One*. 2012; 7(5):1-10.
15. Wei J, Xiong X, Lin Y, Zheng B, Cheng D. Association between serum interleukin-6 concentrations and chronic obstructive pulmonary disease: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *Peer J* 2015; 1-16.
16. Garcia-Rio F, Miravittles M, Soriano JB, Munoz L, Duran-Tauleria E, Sanchez G et al. Systemic inflammation in chronic obstructive pulmonary disease: a population-based study. *Respir Res*. 2010; 11(1):63–77.
17. De Moraes MR, Da Costa AC, Correa K d S, Junqueira-Kipnis AP, Rabahi MF. Interleukin-6 and interleukin-8 blood levels' poor association with the severity and clinical profile of ex-smokers with COPD. *Int J ChronObstruct Pulmon Dis*. 2014; 9:735–743.
18. Bolton CE, Broekhuizen R, Ionescu AA, Nixon LS, Wouters EF, Shale DJ, Schols AM. Cellular protein breakdown and systemic inflammation are unaffected by pulmonary rehabilitation in COPD. *Thorax*. 2007; 62:109–114.
19. Fatma G. M. Hussein, Randa S. Mohammed, Rasha A. Khattab et al. Serum interleukin-6 in chronic obstructive pulmonary disease patients and its relation to severity and acute exacerbation. *The Egyptian Journal of Bronchology*. 2022; 16(10):1-11.
20. Chen CZ, Ou CY, Hsu CH, Hsiue TR. Validation of the GOLD 2013 classification in predicting exacerbations and mortality in Taiwanese patients with chronic obstructive pulmonary disease. *J Formos Med Assoc* 2015; 114:1258–1266.
21. Ashwani Verma, Nachiket G, Uday N Yadav, Manas Pratim Roy, Amreen M, Ravishankar N. Prevalence of COPD among population above 30 years in India: A systematic review and meta-analysis. 2021; 11:1-13.
22. AboEl-Magd GH, Mabrouk MM. Soluble urokinase-type plasminogen activator receptor as a measure of treatment response in acute exacerbation of COPD. *J Bras Pneumol*. 2018; 44(1):36-41.
23. Shaker SB, Dirksen A, Bach KS, Mortensen J. Imaging in chronic obstructive pulmonary disease. *COPD*. 2007; 4(2):143-61.
24. Bocskei RM, Benczur B, Losonczy G, Illyes M, Cziraki A, Muller V et al. Soluble Urokinase-Type Plasminogen Activator Receptor and Arterial Stiffness in Patients with COPD. *Lung*. 2019; 197(2):189-197.
25. James A, Palmer L, Kicic E. Decline in lung function in the Busselton Health Study. *Am J Respir Crit Care Med*. 2005; 171:109–114
26. Haraguchi M, Shimura S, Shirato K. Morphometric analysis of bronchial cartilage in chronic obstructive pulmonary disease and bronchial asthma. *Am J Respir Crit Care Med*. 1999; 159:1005–1013
27. Can U, Guzelant A, Yerlikaya FH, et al. The role of serum soluble urokinase-type plasminogen activator receptor in stable chronic obstructive pulmonary disease. *J Investig Med*. 2014; 62(7):938- 43.
28. Godtfredsen NS, Jørgensen DV, Marsaa K, Ulrik CS, Andersen O, Eugen-Olsen J, Rasmussen LJH. Soluble urokinase plasminogen activator receptor predicts mortality in exacerbated COPD. *Respir Res*. 2018; 19(1):97.
29. Sever ZK, Bircan HA, Sirin FB, Evrimler S, Celik S, Merd N. Serum biomarkers in patients with stable and exacerbated COPD-bronchiectasis overlap syndrome. *Clin Respir J*. 2020; 14(11):1032- 39.
30. De Moraes MR, Da Costa AC, Correa K d S, Junqueira-Kipnis AP, Rabahi MF. Interleukin-6 and interleukin-8 blood levels' poor association with the severity and clinical profile of ex-

- smokers with COPD. *Int J Chron Obstruct Pulmon Dis.* 2014; 9:735–743
31. Wei J, Xiong X, Lin Y, Zheng B, Cheng D. Association between serum interleukin-6 concentrations and chronic obstructive pulmonary disease: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *Peer J.* 2013; 3: e1199.
 32. Singh S, Verma SK, Kumar S, Ahmad MK, Nischal A, et al. Correlation of severity of chronic obstructive pulmonary disease with potential biomarkers. *Immunol Lett.* 2018; 196: 1-10.
 33. Soler N, Ewig S, Torres A, et al. Airway inflammation and bronchial microbial patterns in patients with stable chronic obstructive pulmonary disease. *Eur Respir J.* 1999; 14:1015–1022.
 34. Pinto-Plata VM, Livnat G, Girish M. Systemic cytokines, clinical and physiological changes in patients hospitalized for exacerbation of COPD. *Chest.* 2007; 131:37–43.
 35. Abd El-Maksoud MD, Samy N, EL Khayyal A. Clinical utility of biomarkers as predictors of lung function in chronic obstructive pulmonary disease. *N Y Sci J.* 2010; 3:25–32.
 36. Attaran D, Lari SM, Towhid M, et al. Interleukin-6 and airflow limitation in chemical warfare patients with chronic obstructive pulmonary disease. *Int J Chron Obstruct Pulmon Dis.* 2010; 5:1–6
 37. Ramadan MR, Saadeldin AM, Osman AM, et al. Systemic inflammation in COPD patients. *El-Minia Med Bul.* 2010; 21:255–263.
 38. Akublut HH, Ozden M, Deveci F, Muz MH. IL-6 and IL-8 Levels in Patients with Acute Exacerbations of Chronic Obstructive Pulmonary Disease. *J Clin Diag Res.* 2009; 3:1285-1288.